

THYROID HORMONAL STATUS IN DIFFERENT CLINICAL FORMS OF GLOMERULONEPHRITIS: IMMUNOENDOCRINE AND RENAL CORRELATIONS

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Relevance: The interaction between immune and endocrine systems plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of glomerulonephritis; however, thyroid dysfunction across its clinical forms remains insufficiently characterized.

Objective: To investigate thyroid hormonal status and its relationship with cytokine activity and renal function in patients with various clinical forms of glomerulonephritis.

Materials and Methods: The study included 103 patients with glomerulonephritis (latent, nephrotic, hypertensive, and mixed forms). Serum levels of TSH, free T4, free T3, anti-TPO antibodies, and cytokines were measured by ELISA. Statistical analysis was performed using parametric methods with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: There are numerous regions worldwide characterized by imbalances of trace elements in the environment, which in turn leads to changes in their levels in animals and humans, causing specific diseases associated with metabolic disorders and, as a rule, widespread.

Iodine metabolism disorders, associated with insufficient iodine in ecosystems, have been and remain one of the most pressing problems in modern livestock farming in many countries. They are one of the causes of endemic goiter in humans and animals. Iodine deficiency impairs thyroid function, leading to inadequate production of thyroid hormones. Iodine is an element in the Earth's crust, occurring in all components but not forming independent deposits. Its biogeochemical cycle in nature is determined by its physicochemical properties, which determine its active air and water migration, the properties of natural components, and its participation in the biochemical processes of organisms, which concentrate it in significant quantities and play a key role in the element's transformation in nature.

Iodine's main source is seawater, whose evaporation releases iodine primarily into the atmosphere and then into the soil with precipitation. Depending on the amount of precipitation and the distance from the ocean, iodine can fall annually from 9 to 50 grams per hectare. Marine sediments, especially organogenic silts, are characterized by high iodine content—10-300 mg/kg of dry matter. Because iodine compounds are highly water-soluble, acidic, easily oxidizable, and volatile in their elemental state, accumulation during soil formation occurs in the humus layer, where it is bound primarily by organic matter. It has been established that the richer the soil in organic matter, the more iodine it contains. Therefore, chernozem and peat soils are considered to be rich in this element. Over time, a dynamic equilibrium is established between the atmosphere and the soil, whereby the input of iodine into the soil is compensated by a reverse process and the removal of the element through surface and groundwater runoff.

Laboratory signs of hypothyroidism were detected in 51% of patients with nephrotic glomerulonephritis and in 56.3% of patients with the mixed form, whereas only 17.2% of patients with the hypertensive form demonstrated hypothyroid changes ($p < 0.05$). Thyroid hormones (free T4 and free T3) showed significant negative correlations with IL-1 β , IL-8, ESR,

serum creatinine, and proteinuria, while TSH and anti-TPO antibodies were associated with impaired renal function parameters ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Thyroid hormonal disturbances in glomerulonephritis are clinical-form specific and closely associated with immune-inflammatory activity and renal dysfunction.

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